

MSc in Procurement, Logistics and
Supply Chain Management

Procurement Performance and Its Impact on Operational Efficiency in Bahrain Airport Company

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of Salford for the degree of MSc in Procurement, Logistics and Supply Chain
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ABSTRACT

Procurement is increasingly seen as a crucial strategic task in today's successful organizations, with board-level involvement in purchasing decisions becoming increasingly important. Airports, for example, must adopt integrated procurement techniques to meet their strategic objectives and infrastructure requirements. To address increasing demand, limited resources, and public scrutiny, airports must evaluate their organization's setup, resources, and internal procedures for services handled by external vendors. They must also consider external forces affecting performance and delivery, such as laws, legislation, funding resources, and the needs of airlines, tenants, passengers, and agency departments.

The case study has focused on the evaluation of procurement and operational efficiency at Bahrain Airport Company (BAC) and how they are linked to each other. Mixed-methods strategy was used to gather the data. Qualitative methods included semi-structured interviews with personnel from BAC procurement and operations functions and the analysis of archival documents from BAC and BTB (Bahrain Tender Board) websites. Quantitative methods include the DEA analysis for the operational efficiency of BAC and comparing the results with those of other airports in the region.

The study assesses BAC's procurement performance with a particular emphasis on lead time, cost savings, and request response. It implies that supplier selection and strategic sourcing may enhance organizational performance, resulting in lower costs and increased profitability. Through cost optimization and developing strong partnerships with suppliers, the procurement function is in line with the company's objectives. Additionally, the study assesses the operational efficiency of BAC, emphasizing passenger throughput, processing zone capacity, and slot utilization. It has been demonstrated that procurement and operational efficiency are linked, highlighting the significance of strategic sourcing and cost control initiatives leading to more cost-effective and efficient operations.

Key Words: Operational Efficiency, Procurement Function, Public Procurement, Procurement Performance.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AI (Artificial Intelligence)

Bahrain Airport Company (BAC)

Bahrain Dinar (BHD)

Bahrain International Airport (BIA)

Bahrain Tender Board (TBT)

BoQs (Bills of Quantity)

CBB (Central Bank of Bahrain)

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

Data-Driven Decision Making (DDDM)

Decision Making Unit (DMU)

Dubai International Airport (DXB)

DEA (Data Envelopment Analysis)

Gulf Air Group Holding (GFG)

Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC)

Hamad International Airport (HIA)

King Khaled International Airport (KKIA)

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators)

ML (Machine Learning)

Muscat International Airport (MCT)

On-Time Performance (OTP)

RFPs (Requests for Proposals)

RTS (Return to Scales)

Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA)

TRA (Telecommunications Regulatory Authority).

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Chapter 1: Introduction:

1.1 Introduction

Many of the successful organizations of today view procurement as a task of significant strategic importance. Because the strategic role and contribution of purchasing and supply are now widely acknowledged in many major commercial concerns, strategic purchasing decisions may now be made through involvement in purchasing at the board level rather than by a departmental manager. The importance of purchasing has increased consistently over the past 50 years, with recent years seeing a sharp rise in interest in the function (Baily et al., 2015).

An airport's main function is to bring together people, procedures, technology, public and private organizations, locations, artifacts, and data to facilitate scheduled flight arrival and departure. Due to the complexity of their operations, airport companies must adopt procurement techniques and systems in an integrated, uniform manner in order to meet their strategic objectives. To guarantee that airport companies meet their obligations regarding airport infrastructure requirements, the procurement function is essential (Motaung & Sifolo, 2023). It is crucial to evaluate how the organization is set up and what resources are available to satisfy those objectives as airport corporations attempt to address expanding demand, decreasing resources, and increasing public scrutiny. The company needs to reassess what services are best handled internally and what procedures are in place to procure and manage services that

will be handled by outside vendors. The airport companies also need to be aware of external forces affecting expectations of performance and delivery of the services, including laws, legislation, labor agreements, funding resources, budgetary obligations, and the needs of airlines, tenants, passengers, and agency departments (Defant et al., 2013).

1.2 Background:

Bahrain International Airport (BIA) is the only airport in Bahrain and is the entry point through which the kingdom is connected with the rest of the world. It has been operated and managed by Bahrain Airport Company (BAC) since 2010. Thanks to the 210,000 square meters of space in the new passenger terminal, which opened in 2021, Bahrain International Airport can now accommodate 14 million passengers annually and 130,000 air traffic movements, with a peak hour bag handling capacity of 4,700 (Bahrain Airport Company, 2021). Bahrain Airport Company (BAC) is a fully owned subsidiary of Gulf Air Group Holding (GFG). The Ministry of Transportation and Telecommunications, along with BAC, was tasked with creating the airport's facilities, infrastructure, and services. The result is BIA now being the most cutting-edge airport in the Gulf. BIA's advantageous location in the Gulf has given it convenient access to the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) market. A growing number of airlines use the airport, and it serves as a regional hub for international cargo companies like DHL, which has had its Middle East headquarters in Bahrain since the 1980s. In accordance with Bahrain's Vision 2030, BIA continues to promote the aviation industry's growth, boost the image of Bahrain as a business-friendly nation, and create new

employment opportunities that support the nation's economy (Ministry of Transportation and Telecommunications, 2023).

The Bahrain Tender Board (TBT), which was founded in 2002 as an independent regulator of government procurement processes in the nation, oversees bids and acquisitions made by the BAC. In order to promote effective and efficient government procurement procedures and systems, the Tender Board employs a strict regulatory framework designed to ensure the greatest fairness and equality of opportunity. To preserve equality, transparency, and competition in all government procurement processes, it collaborates with local, regional, and worldwide contractors and suppliers as well as public sector purchasing bodies (Bahrain Tender Board, 2020).

The BIA has cemented its position as a prominent aviation center thanks to its unparalleled location, aviation advancements, and competitive edge. The Kingdom's tolerance of other cultures allows for thriving commerce and business. Additionally, as compared to other countries in the region, Bahrain has the shortest transit times between its seaport, airport, and logistics processing zone. This offers a critical competitive edge for serving Middle Eastern markets. Regarding connection, a plane can take passengers from any major city in the GCC to another in about an hour, and it is simple to travel by road via Saudi Arabia's Eastern Province. Additionally, it links over 250 million people in just two hours (Bahrain Airport Company, 2023). These factors, in addition to the increase in air traffic in the Gulf region and the widespread use of Middle Eastern airports as important transit hubs between the East and the West, have all

contributed to the need to expand and modernize BIA in order to compete with other top airports in the region that cater to this demand.

1.3 Significance of the Study:

Although limited studies have investigated the procurement performance and operational efficiency of airports in developing countries, there are no papers that discuss the procurement performance and its impact on the operational efficiency of airport companies in the region. This paper seeks to fill the research gap by evaluating the procurement process and the operational efficiency of BAC and establishing a relationship between its procurement performance and operational efficiency. The study's goal is to assist policymakers by providing them with knowledge that will help them increase operational efficiency by using better procurement techniques. The findings might help in performance improvement by identifying existing gaps and providing recommendations to mitigate them. The many stakeholders involved in the region's airport business may find the insights and recommendations reached from the study to be of great use. The findings might be useful to scholars, students, and the general public, especially those who might be interested in the procurement field. Additionally, the research will broaden the existing knowledge on the subject and encourage new research in the area.

1.4 Problem Statement:

The procurement function has a major impact on the overall organization's performance and profitability, and weak procurement procedures could lead to a

decline in overall performance (Yeboah et al., 2022). Due to a lack of information regarding the procurement process, procurement departments tend to struggle to assess the efficiency of the process. Given the link between public sector performance and its procurement function, heightened oversight of the industry is justified. All public organizations, regardless of size or level of government, must make sure that goods and services are procured efficiently in order to fulfill their duty to serve the public. If the procurement function is unable to deliver high-quality goods and services in a timely manner and at an affordable price, the government's performance deteriorates (Coggburn, 2023).

Many stakeholders anticipate that procurement processes will guarantee cost-effectiveness and fast budget execution. Too much emphasis is frequently placed on procedural compliance at the expense of performance to maximize the return on investment. It is believed that procurement has become a bottleneck for the provision of services because government agencies end up with unspent balances because of lengthy procurement processes. Even though achieving full compliance with the law will not be sufficient if the prices are higher than the market price (Komakech, 2016).

This calls for rigid procedures and performance standards to solve this issue and to give decision-makers in BAC information about the procurement function and its impact on operational efficiency. The decision-makers in the procurement department can receive reliable information about how the procurement function is doing and how it affects company operations when appropriate benchmarks are defined. Bahrain has invested a huge amount of public funds to build the

new BIA terminal to compete with its neighboring nations as a major hub in the region, and in return, it expects the airport to perform to the highest standard. The scope of the study is limited to BAC, which operates BIA. With a handling capacity of 4,700 bags per hour, the airport's 210,000 square meters can accommodate 14 million passengers and 130,000 air traffic movements annually (Bahrain Airport Company, 2021). In 2022, it handled nearly 7 million passengers, 82,000 aircraft traffic movements, and 379,000 tons of cargo (Bahrain Airport Company, 2023). BAC has generated a total revenue of \$85,597,000 and currently employs 377 staff (Kona Equity, 2023).

1.5 Research Aim:

The main aim of the study is to determine the impact of BAC's procurement performance on its operational efficiency.

1.6 Research Objectives:

The study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. To evaluate the procurement performance of BAC.
2. To evaluate the operational efficiency of BAC.
3. To establish a link between the procurement function and the operational efficiency of BAC.

1.7 Research Questions:

1. How can the procurement performance of BAC be measured?
2. How can the operational efficiency of BAC be measured?

3. What is the relationship between procurement performance and operational efficiency in BAC?

1.8 Chapter Summary:

To summarize, the chapter has provided a general introduction and background to the topic. Later, the significance of the study was discussed alongside the problem statement. Finally, the chapter presented the research aims, research objectives, and research questions.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction:

A literature review is an impartial, comprehensive, and condensed critical evaluation of the relevant research and non-research publications on the topic. Its goals are to inform the reader about the current status of the literature on the subject and lay the foundation for further goals, including arguing for more field research (Hart, 1998). The review of the literature was used to gather information from earlier studies that would improve general understanding of the many concepts covered by the study questions.

This chapter highlights several studies relating to procurement performance, operational efficiency, and their relationship in organizations. As the paper aims to establish a link between procurement performance and operational efficiency in BAC, the independent variable is specified as procurement performance, which influences operational efficiency, which is considered the dependent variable. Additionally covered in this chapter are the functions of procurement, public procurement, and airport operations.

Figure 1: Independent & Dependent Variables Conceptual Framework

2.2 SWOT Analysis:

A SWOT analysis is to be conducted describing strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats that face BAC. It is a helpful instrument that enables the examination of the organization's environment and the identification of the resources that have an impact on it (Pickton & Wright, 1998).

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The strategic geographic location of Bahrain. • New terminal with increased capacity.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bahrain has the shortest transit times between its seaport, airport, and logistics processing zone. • Bahrain has convenient connectivity to all GCC countries.
Weaknesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The pandemic has slowed down the aviation industry in the past few years. • Change in consumer travel habits.
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The new terminal allows for additional capacity for tourists, airlines, and destinations. • A rise in Bahrain's tourist numbers over the previous year. (Bahrain Airport Company, 2023).
Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competition from neighbouring countries. • Political uncertainties in the region. • Current economic situation in the world.

Figure 2: SWOT Analysis for Factors Influencing BAC

2.3 Procurement Performance:

Management must be able to assess the efficacy and efficiency of actions in order to compare outcomes to expectations, motivate, direct, and enhance decision-making. This is accomplished through the use of performance measurement, a critical tool. The degree to which purchasing can support the organization's intended levels of innovation, quality, flexibility, and cost determines purchasing performance on a strategic level. On an operational level, procurement performance can be determined by the degree to which procurement operations succeed in securing the supply of commodities in accordance with the demands of internal customers (Lardenoije et al., 2005).

Benchmarking in the purchasing function considerably boosts purchasing performance, according to a study by Sanchez-Rodriguez et al. (2003). The study also provided evidence in support of the notion that companies with strong purchasing performance also exhibit strong business performance. Having a formal process in place to benchmark prices, quality levels, and other relevant purchasing performance indicators with other companies' purchasing processes improves performance through higher levels of purchased material quality, vendor delivery performance, internal customer satisfaction, and inventory performance. The financial performance of the company is expected to be enhanced by this result (return on assets, gross margin, and market share).

Caniato et al. (2012) argued that as the company's purchasing strategy plays a strategic role, performance measurement is essential to managing this function in line with the corporate plan as a whole. For a variety of reasons, it is essential to evaluate purchasing operations. It allows for prospective comparisons with

other companies, enhances decision-making based on plans and outcomes, shares objectives and duties within the purchasing organization, and inspires individuals and molds their behavior through performance feedback.

Pohl & Foerstl (2011) claim that purchasing performance systems that provide a direct connection between financial performance and non-financial performance measurement are crucial to supporting the planned diverse strategic objectives beyond recurrent cost savings. For these measuring methods to meet the necessary level of pre-defined strategic performance parameters, category-level modifications to purchasing processes are necessary. They suggest that purchasing performance measurement should be used to fulfill five various sorts of roles, including those in strategy management, performance assessment, behavior impact, learning and improvement, and communication. Beamon (1998) claims that prior studies show that firms frequently utilize expenses exclusively as a performance metric. This occurs as a result of how easily performance can be measured using just one indicator, despite the fact that this practice only offers cursory details about reality. Beamon (1996) also claims that indicators must also concurrently demonstrate inclusiveness (to measure all relevant features), universality (to enable comparison under various functioning circumstances), measurability (to ensure that the vital information is measurable), and consistency (to ensure that the metrics used are in line with the organization's goals).

Van Weele (2014) suggests that four dimensions should be used to measure performance in order to provide a complete picture of purchasing performance:

1- Price/Cost Dimension: It describes how prices are kept track of and assessed when suppliers impose them. Budgets for materials, reports on price inflation, and deviation reports are a few examples of metrics. The key goal is to keep an eye on the costs to avoid significant price hikes. It also refers to cost or price reduction, which is used to describe the systematic monitoring of cost-cutting measures. Cost reduction may arise from value analysis, coordination of purchasing requirements amongst business divisions, or increasing competition by introducing new suppliers or alternatives to the purchase process.

2- Product/Quality Dimension: This refers to the function of procurement in new product development and general quality assurance. The total number of hours put into creative projects, the total number of hours vendors allocate to projects, and the overall lead time of the projects are the three primary areas of purchasing's involvement in new product development. The consistency of the delivered items with the standards is the primary emphasis of purchasing's involvement in overall quality control. Among the factors that are regularly measured are the percentage of incoming items that are rejected, the number of certified suppliers, and the number of supplier quality agreements. How much assurance the company offers that the materials coming from its suppliers are appropriate should be stated in the metrics.

3- Logistics Dimension: It focuses on the role that procurement should play in boosting the effectiveness of acquired materials. According to theory, it is judged in accordance with three key criteria: control over the prompt and accurate

management of purchase orders, suppliers' delivery schedules, and supplied quantities.

4- Organizational Dimension: This is the terminology used to describe the methods used to carry out the goals of the purchasing function. The segments are purchasing management, purchasing information systems, purchasing information systems, and purchasing staff.

2.4 Operational Efficiency:

Operational efficiency refers to the actions that each operation along the supply chain can take to decrease its own complexity, minimize the cost of doing business with other operations along the supply chain, and speed up throughput. Throughput is made simpler throughout the entire chain as a result of these individual acts. A chain's activities would become more reliable and would move more quickly, both of which help to lessen supply chain fluctuations (Slack et al., 2013). The fundamental strategic aims of the companies are supported by operational efficiency. Operational efficiency in a business setting is the ratio of outputs realized by a firm to the input required to execute a business operation. The output-input ratio improves as operation efficiency increases. Typically, operational efficiency is attained by streamlining a company's fundamental processes so that it can adapt to continuously changing market conditions more quickly and affordably (Hillier, 2012).

Operational effectiveness supports the organizations' primary strategic goals. Realizing operational efficiency is essential for enhancing customer satisfaction

and increasing shareholder value. Therefore, improving operational efficiency should be one of the top priorities for businesses. Research by Hussein (2014) has concluded that an increase in maximized resource utilization and waste minimization will lead to an increase in procurement performance. As operational efficiency contributes to cost reduction, a business can improve its cash flow, profitability, and competitiveness as a result (Oral & Yolalan, 1990). Sufian (2007) asserts that increasing operational effectiveness directly affects an organization's profit margins and that efficient businesses are more cost-effective. In order to achieve sound and long-term financial success, managers of any sort of firm must take operational efficiency into account.

Organizations are being compelled by an increasing number of factors to improve operational efficiency and make sure their operational procedures are efficient. This entails the requirement to supply value-adding goods or services of excellent quality, promptly, and affordably. Because operational effectiveness is a crucial component in determining how well a business operates, organizations pursuing these objectives need to pay special attention to it. Establishing procedures based on significant organizational competencies is what constitutes operational effectiveness (Knott & Medina, 2012).

Businesses may increase operational efficiency by cutting down on waste and repetition while maximizing the assets that ultimately lead to their success. They can also do this by making the most of their staff, innovation, and company procedures. Lower internal expenses brought on by operational efficiency help

businesses compete more successfully in fiercely competitive marketplaces, resulting in larger profit margins (Abdel-Magied et al., 2020).

When evaluating a company's operational efficiency, the inputs and outputs are the main points of attention. A number of strategies, including both parametric and nonparametric approaches and ratio measurements, can be used to assess an organization's operational efficiency.

1- Ratio measures: Numerous ratio indicators can be constructed by taking into account a range of resource inputs, including labor, capital, material, and energy. However, because there are so few of them, operational efficiency as a whole cannot be accurately represented by them. In recent years, more appropriate measures for complete ratio indicators have been developed. It is nonetheless difficult to reach unbiased findings because there are several evaluations (Braglia et al., 2003).

2- Parametric techniques: Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA) is the most common parametric approach; it employs a stochastic approach to evaluate the frontier parametrically. The method is stochastic; it also takes a random variable into account. According to this approach, inefficiencies and random errors both contribute to production function deviations (Bezaf, 2009).

3- Non-parametric techniques: One of the most popular ways to gauge operational effectiveness is via DEA (Data Envelopment Analysis). In order to determine which service providers can offer services at the highest level or the lowest level with a given set of inputs, it employs a linear programming method.

The method looks at a company's input or output volume. It can be used to identify the most effective methods for allocating resources among businesses. (Steering Committee for the Review of Commonwealth/State Service Provision, 1997).

2.5 Relationship between Procurement Performance & Operational Efficiency:

The awareness that the value created by a purchase may be increased through efficient process management is largely responsible for the shift from the traditional strategy of material supply to the idea of comprehensive procurement. According to Quayle (2006), effective procurement ought to address both sides of the profit equation by increasing an item's ability to create income and lowering its ownership costs. It is clear that using these tactics will improve the efficiency of procurement and overall operational efficiency. Not only will well-managed procurement result in cost reduction and the most efficient fulfillment of supply requirements, but it will also contribute to a boost in net income and profitability. Nevertheless, it is only through the establishment of goals and the tracking of progress toward those goals that the effectiveness of any corporate objective can be evaluated.

Alsafar (2022) argues that the intricate procurement process can increase business efficiency. Given that their products and services will be procured at the ideal level of quality, quantity, and cost and delivered "just in time," firms will not have to stockpile supplies and spare parts. Fewer resources will be needed to store the products if there are fewer of them. Additionally, it guarantees that they

are not moved excessively, which lessens the chance of their being destroyed and minimizes the need for additional resources. Buying goods of the right quality guarantees that they are both cost-efficient and effective in the function for which they are intended. Since the components and goods will not be of inferior quality, there will be less chance that they will cause issues.

An organization's success is determined by how well it accomplishes its objectives, which may include both long-term improvements in market share and short-term increases in productivity and inventory reduction. A corporation may be able to offer its clients the same benefit at a cheaper cost or better service at a given cost, depending on the resource's level of efficiency (Barney, 1991). Other companies in the same industry are used to measure the organization's effectiveness. The growth of market share and return on investment are two indicators of an organization's performance. The purchasing department faces many risks and obstacles as a result of using insufficient criteria. Determining the end user's simplest essential criteria makes it possible for a transparent method of purchasing goods or services and evaluating them. This ensures that specifications are met at the least expensive overall achievable. It is possible to reduce the cost of purchases in two ways: by enhancing supply chain management and by professionalizing the procurement role within companies (Edvardsson, 1998).

According to Onyango's (2014) research, proper procurement planning can increase an organization's general effectiveness and efficiency. Ultimately, it is likely that a variety of variables, such as the intricate procurement standards and

procedures at stake, the organizational structure and manner of leadership, as well as the specific objectives adopted by the organization, will affect how the procurement strategy impacts organizational performance. Organizations have prioritized costs or savings as the only indicator or measure of performance, according to Kakwezi & Nyoko (2019). The purchasing function will be applauded if costs go down and criticized if savings go down. It seems that the purchasing function was developed with the intention of increasing efficiency while reducing costs. Financial indicators do not take into account market dynamics or how complex it is to buy products and services for public entities. Recent improvements in purchasing make it essential that what is measured is not only relevant to the company but also should include all essential procurement-related variables. Predicting needs, sourcing, monitoring supply, and other procurement actions all help to improve operational efficiency. Successful procurement procedures are ones that maximize value while satisfying end-user needs.

There are three main procurement concepts, according to Caldwell et al. (2009). The first principle is transparency, which guarantees all phases of the procurement process are correctly and precisely documented. Secondly, accountability highlights the need to answer to financiers, who might have rules that must be observed when using the funds that they have given. The third concept is effectiveness and efficiency, and it covers the "six rights" of procurement (right source, right price, right quantity, right time, right place, and right quality).

2.6 Procurement Function:

In order to accomplish its strategic goals, a corporation must be able to identify, access, and effectively handle any outside resources it might need. This falls within the authority of the procurement business management function. The fundamental goal of procurement is to make sure there is a steady flow of goods and services to help organizations run properly (Lyson & Farrington, 2020). The procurement role has changed a lot in the modern economy because companies are competing in a global market and technology is changing rapidly. This has led to a rise in the business impact of procurement, especially for companies that have to compete in fast-paced business environments. And, to keep up with customer demands, procurement needs to be more sensitive to customer needs as well as to other areas of the business.

Baily et al. (2015) argued that in recent years, senior management in organizations has emphasized measuring procurement and supply chain functions and therefore has become more likely to support their development as important determinants in cost reduction and reaching organizational goals. As the amount of attention paid to procurement increases, the focus of organizations shifts towards more strategic activities, like developing long-term relationships with suppliers and reducing costs overall. The level of development of purchasing activity has an impact on an organization's capacity to reduce expenses and eventually remove them from the supply chain. Knoppen & Sáenz (2015) cite the development of new products and markets as well as strategic advantages related to the firm's value proposition as examples of how

purchasing may play a strategic role in an organization. This highlights purchasing's non-financial contribution. Performance may take on various forms, depending on the value proposition, including pricing (cost), quality, delivery, diversity, innovation, and sustainability.

According to a paper by Carr & Pearson (2002), the involvement of suppliers must be considered when elevating the function of purchasing to a level of strategic importance. Raising the purchasing role from a non-strategic to a strategic one has benefits from a management standpoint. Increased potential for the purchasing department to contribute to the long-term prosperity of the business is one of these benefits. Strategic purchasing is something that cutting-edge companies aim to have since they know how important it is to the achievement of their objectives. The purchasing function must participate in strategy planning in a similar way to how manufacturing and marketing do. Most companies are thought to understand the significance of strategic performance because they invest a significant portion of their revenue in purchased input.

A strategic purchasing department can help a company preserve its competitive advantage in a variety of ways; cost management is the first benefit. Effective control of input cost costs immediately affects a company's bottom-line profit. Second, it gives the company essential data about supply trends that will help with goal setting and decision-making. Third, it develops strong relationships with suppliers to enhance the effectiveness of material quality and delivery (Hogan & Armstrong, 2011). Building trusted relationships with suppliers can urge them to be accommodating and supportive in the event of a sudden rise in business

requirements, which is one crucial role that procurement plays for businesses (Alsafar, 2022). Therefore, a strategic purchasing function aims to balance achieving the company's expectations with aligning its capabilities with the competitive edge that the organization seeks. Only when it is properly established can procurement contribute to supply chain management's operational, tactical, and strategic advancements. Any business should be capable of boosting efficiency and efficacy in the supply or value chain if certain organizations' procurement departments can do so when operating strategically and pro-actively.

According to Saunders (1997), a viewpoint on the purchasing and supply function that is characterized by involvement in primarily administrative, order-placing activities and in which staff members typically only implement a short-term hand-to-mouth strategy, simply reacting to contingencies as they arise, is at one end of the spectrum. On the other hand, a long-term, strategic strategy is developed to influence the path of the sourcing and supply plan, and urgent demands are managed in light of these concerns. Movements in the direction of the procurement function's determinants and their significance to organizational effectiveness enable this.

Similar practices highlight for the entire organization the strategic significance of excellence in purchasing and supply chain management. Suppliers generally contribute to the final phase of a company's apparent success. The supply chain's design and the actions of company partners may be influenced by the purchasing strategies of more powerful companies.

2.7 Public Procurement:

Public procurement is the practice of buying items for the completion of construction projects and services with money from state budgets, local authority budgets, loans backed by the state, and earnings from state-owned enterprises (Komakech, 2016). One of the most effective instruments the government has for satisfying popular needs is public procurement, which raises the standard of living of the general public by providing goods or services and ensuring value for money. A country's economy and public spending are significantly impacted by public procurement, which also serves as a key gauge of a government's effectiveness (Motaung & Sifolol, 2023).

It appears that a successful public procurement system has both procurement goals and non-procurement aims, regardless of a country's economic, social, or political status. The procurement function's objectives often include quality, promptness, overall cost, reducing business, economic, and technological risks, fostering competition, and ensuring transparency. Although there are many non-procurement goals, a few of them are concerned with economics (preferring domestic or local businesses); other examples include the environment (or "green procurement"), social issues (assisting woman-owned and minority-owned businesses interests), and international affairs. Because there are always compromises between these objectives, it can be challenging for politicians and public procurement experts to select the optimal one (Thai, 2001).

McCrudden (2004) concurred that public procurement has frequently been used to advance public policies in a number of fields, such as the national policy on

industry, reducing unemployment, improving working conditions, supporting small businesses, supporting local businesses, empowering disabled workers, and supporting equal payment for men and women. When using public funds, public agencies must carry out effective procurement in order to provide superior services and protect the general public's interests. The ideas of transparency and accountability are more important than anywhere else in public administration when it comes to procurement, which, according to Schapper et al. (2006), may make up more than a third of all government spending.

Organizations or governments will not be able to develop the organizations, indicators of performance, management instruments, or expertise necessary to meet the full range of political and social demands until they fully understand the proper scope of public procurement and strike a balance between process, performance, and strategic imperatives. In the absence of a coherent framework, it is anticipated that government reforms will continue to be fragmentary and cyclical.

Any public procurement effort may be impacted by competing conformity management and performance management aims, either of which may be at odds with more general strategic political goals or reform. According to Siyal & Xin (2019), the public procurement process is supported by five fundamental principles: value for money which is a concept that requires public organizations to consider developing their policies and procedures at a time when they will see the best returns on their investments. Ethics, which explains how procurement professionals are expected to adhere to ethical conduct to a greater degree than

other professionals; competition, which involves making purchases of products and services through competitive bidding. Transparency, which refers to the openness of the procurement system, ensures accountability and minimizes corruption. And finally, accountability, which explores how managers in public sector firms must contend with circumstances that are more competitive and simultaneously answer to the public, which constantly require accountability and improved goods and services.

Following a six-step process is believed to increase the likelihood that public procurement reform will be successful, as per Walker (2003). It includes: the promotion of the new system's benefits; the interaction of the public and private sectors, which results in a greater knowledge of one another's problems and needs; the need for an effective procurement training program in order to improve staff abilities and familiarize suppliers with the demands of the system; the highest level of political support; the establishment of a sole agency for public procurement to manage the nation's general policy-making and public procurement; and the creation of effective primary and secondary procurement legislation. These steps are necessary for any organizational change in public entities to be successful because they remove any uncertainty over the government's commitment to reform.

2.8 Airport Operations:

Air operations are the everyday tasks that must be carried out simultaneously in an airport in order to safely transfer both domestic and foreign passengers.

These tasks, which start even before an aircraft takes off, include planning,

getting ready, ensuring safety, providing training, facilitating commerce, and dealing with issues pertaining to the airport, airlines, and passengers (Cumberbatch, 2016). As the physical location where a modal transfer from air to land transport or vice versa takes place, the airport is an essential part of the air transportation system. It acts as a hub for communication between the airport, airlines, and travelers—the three key components of the aviation industry. Effective airport design and administration must take into account the interplay between these three crucial system actors (Ashford et al., 2013).

Airports and ground service providers need to maximize their available resources in order to stay on top of the latest developments. The personnel and machinery utilized for ground handling at the terminal and on the ramp, as well as the infrastructure and resources of the building, are all examples of this. Minimizing waste from limited air traffic flow control slots is also crucial. When the work is made more challenging by frequent changes to the flight schedule, such as delays, reroutes, or aircraft changes, tough optimization difficulties typically occur at the tactical planning and online control levels (Kazda & Hromádka, 2011). For airport firms to successfully develop and manage their businesses, they need to acquire goods and services efficiently. There is a lot of cooperation and coordination among airport enterprises since strategic alliances are frequently used to manage daily operations and provide for all stakeholders. Achieving the strategic objectives of airport firms depends on integrating procurement processes and sustainability systems in a uniform manner due to the complexity of airport companies (Motaung & Sifolol, 2023).

Creating an adequate performance measurement system for international airports is difficult since they are dynamic and complex organizations. The creation of performance assessment systems is a crucial management effort since it is complicated by various interconnected issues (airlines, passengers, handling agents, etc.). The improvement of operational performance is becoming more crucial to all parties involved in the air transportation infrastructure. While their customers require that services are delivered in an effective and efficient way to meet their needs (Humphreys & Francis, 2002).

Airport performance can be assessed and compared using a range of variables. When comparing outcomes, it is crucial to take into account variables such as the number of travelers, limitations on capacity, the combination of international and domestic traffic, the mix of both local and transfer passengers, the mix of passenger carrier service (network, low cost, charter), the mix of passengers compared to cargo movement, the level of outsourced services, the variety of facilities provided by the airport, and airport development initiatives (Bottiger et al., 2018). According to Doganis (1992), performance metrics are necessary to ascertain the financial status, measure the performance of, and assess the management of the airport's use of its resources. The effectiveness of various airport departments can be compared with one another and with other airports using performance measurement. Oum et al. (2013) argue that there are three ways to boost operational effectiveness: increasing competition, which would eventually encourage airports to do so because airlines and passengers would have more options; providing airport executives greater autonomy and

responsibility to reorganize operations and manage their businesses; and minimizing redundancy and bureaucracy between the corporate management of airports and governmental administration.

In order to describe the performance metrics at various airports throughout the world, Asker & Battal (2017) have cited a number of studies. Using the number of runways, gates, terminal spaces, staff, parking space, and luggage collecting bands as inputs and the number of passengers and flights, as well as cargo volume, as outputs, are some examples of performance measurement in US airports. The utilization of the quantity of employees, the amount of money invested, and the number of devices as inputs and the overall number of passengers, flights, and total load as outputs in Spanish airports is another illustration of a performance assessment. Stichhauerova & Pelloneova (2019) have used the number of staff, the number of runways, and the size of the airport as inputs in their analysis of the performance of 13 German airports. As outputs, it was decided to use the quantity of cargo and the number of aircraft movements.

Lubbe et al. (2011) assert that passengers' feedback is the main metric that should be used to assess airports. Neglecting customer expectations in service quality measurement might lead airport management to attempt to improve services in a way that is insignificant to passengers. Therefore, it is important to look at what passengers anticipate from airport services and determine how satisfied they are with them.

2.9 Conclusion:

While several studies have focused on the role of procurement and operational efficiency, there are no papers that have looked at the relationship between procurement and operational efficiency in airports in the region. Hussein (2014) investigated the correlation between procurement function performance and operational effectiveness in Kenya's telecoms sector. Asker & Battal (2017) have reviewed the operational efficiency of various airports in the world. Alhasan (2021) has researched Bahrain's public e-procurement system for the road industry. The advantages and challenges of digital procurement in airports in South Africa have been examined by Motaung & Sifolo (2023). Komakech's (2016) study focuses on the effectiveness of public procurement in emerging nations. From this, it may be inferred that no research has looked specifically at how procurement affects operating efficiency in the airports in the region.

The literature review has covered the connection between operational effectiveness and procurement as well as their functions within businesses. The strategic effectiveness of purchasing is determined by how well it can support the organization's planned levels of innovation, quality, flexibility, and cost. Having a formal process in place to compare prices, levels of quality, and other pertinent purchasing performance indicators with those of other businesses significantly improves purchasing performance. Effective purchase processes also lead to higher levels of purchased material quality, vendor delivery performance, internal customer satisfaction, and inventory performance. Profitability directly correlates with operational effectiveness, and cost-effective

businesses perform better overall. The naturally variable levels of resource efficiency have an impact on procurement performance because they enable companies to better serve their customers at a given cost or to get the same result for less money. The specific procurement standards and processes at stake, the organizational framework and approach to leadership, as well as the particular goals and objectives established by the company, will probably all have an impact on how procurement planning affects organizational performance.

Public procurement and airport operations roles have also been covered in the literature review. Both procurement goals and non-procurement goals appear to be present in a competent public procurement system. Public bodies using public funds must carry out efficient procurement with stringent ethical standards in order to provide superior services and safeguard the public interests. When the public and private sectors work together to better understand one another's concerns, and when public procurement has the support of the highest levels of government, its reform is most likely to be successful. Additionally, a central public procurement office should be established for overall policymaking, public procurement oversight, and the development of primary and secondary procurement legislation.

The airport is a crucial component of the system since it serves as the point of contact between passengers, airlines, and other airports—the three primary elements of the air transportation system. Proper airport design and administration must take into account the interplay between these three crucial

system actors. In order to keep up with developments, airports and ground service providers must make the most use of their resources. A variety of indicators were described in order to assess the efficiency of airport operations and create standards for comparison with other airports.

2.10 Summary:

To summarize, the performance of the procurement process, operational efficiency, and their interaction within the business are all covered in this chapter. Several studies were presented to help establish the link between the two variables. The chapter also discusses the role of procurement in organizations and how it can influence their overall performance and profitability. Finally, the chapter covers various views on the significance and role of public procurement and the impact of airport operations on the functioning of an airport.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Chapter 3: Research Methodology:

3.1 Introduction:

The study's research methodology is covered in this chapter. It describes the research methodology and the qualitative and quantitative methods that were employed. It also discusses methods followed in order to collect, examine, and evaluate the data.

3.2 Research Design/ Approach/ Philosophy:

Primary research was conducted by gathering new data to answer particular research questions. Primary data are unpublished facts that have not been altered at all, as they were taken directly from a source. Researchers tend to use a range of strategies to collect and organize primary data for the purpose of achieving a specific goal. Utilizing primary sources enables the researcher to add more details as necessary during the study process and aids in obtaining high-quality data that can enhance results (Taherdoost, 2021). A case study approach was selected, which is a comprehensive analysis of a current topic in its actual setting. In a case study research design, a specific event, circumstance, organization, or social unit is thoroughly and intensively examined (Yin, 1994).

A mixed-methods strategy was used for the study, combining quantitative and qualitative methods. Utilizing both methods gives the research an analytical approach and balances out the shortcomings of one method with those of the

other (Miles et al., 2013). A mixed-methods approach combines post-positivism with interpretivism, combining quantitative and qualitative data to clearly communicate the problems with research. The benefits of this strategy for solving difficult research problems are numerous. Additionally, it provides a logical foundation, methodological adaptability, and a strong comprehension of simpler problems. It is simpler to generalize the findings and consequences of the researched concepts to the general public when researchers employ mixed methods since it allows them to sufficiently deepen and widen their reactions to research themes (Dawadi et al., 2021).

3.3 Data Collection:

3.3.1 Qualitative Methods:

Semi-structured interviews were conducted to gain further insight into the participants' commitment to the operational effectiveness and procurement department KPIs, as well as how they can make sure they are applying the best practices in this area. Semi-structured interviews are carried out to elicit participants' subjective opinions about a certain scenario or event they have experienced. Any comments made by the interviewee to these open-ended questions may be further discussed. This methodology's semi-structured component is made up of this framework and the adaptability of the responses. Due to the problem's relevance and participant-responsiveness, it stands out among interview techniques (McIntosh & Morse, 2015).

The interviewees were selected through the use of purposeful sampling, which entails conducting interviews with a pre-selected, readily identifiable group of

elites who have been selected according to specific criteria. Due to the researcher's presumption that certain demographic groups may have a distinctive, noteworthy, or significant viewpoint on the issue in question based on his prior conceptual understanding of the topic under study, their participation in the sample must be assured (Robinson, 2014). The ability of the respondent to provide information pertinent to the research issue was taken into account when choosing a sample for qualitative research. In order to prevent gathering erroneous or insufficient data, the researcher must utilize judgment based on the best available evidence to choose participants who have sufficient knowledge, sufficient recollection, and the ability to give precise answers to questions (Brink, 1993).

The estimated population of the study was fifteen (15) participants, consisting of personnel with leading roles in the procurement and operations functions of BAC with at least 5 years of experience in their respective fields. By considering their total years of experience and depth of knowledge in the field, the participants were carefully selected. Also, the participants who were obtained have a thorough understanding of the current laws and regulations governing tenders and purchases in Bahrain. The interviews were designed to offer in-depth insights from professionals with solid expertise in the area of public procurement and operations. This sample technique would support the validity of the other methods employed in this study and be effective in eliciting the opinions of public officials with specialized knowledge.

Gentles et al. (2015) recommend that smaller samples be employed in qualitative research. This is probably the case, as the main goal of sampling in qualitative research, in contrast to quantitative research, is to collect information that is useful for understanding the level of complexity, depth, variety, or significance of a phenomenon. Finding a sample that would yield comprehensive and insightful results while avoiding unneeded participant stress and the consumption of limited resources, such as time and cost, is the main challenge for researchers.

Young and Casey's (2018) research provides convincing proof and encouragement that, in some cases, even with small sample sizes, researchers may achieve accurate results. In addition to reducing participant burden, this would help maximize the use of limited resources. Also understudied are the sample sizes required to achieve theme and code saturation across various qualitative approaches or data processing techniques. This indicates that small samples of carefully obtained qualitative data may accurately capture the complete spectrum of individual perspectives, whereas bigger sample sizes can only slightly increase relevance. Thus, the targeted sample size was 5-6 personnel, while the actual sample size is 5.

Online interviewing was chosen as a method since it can be done whenever it is convenient for both the interviewer and the respondent. The use of online interviewing is innovative and timesaving; researchers now have more opportunities to apply online research methodologies as more people use the internet. The convenience and cost savings of conducting research online

benefit both the researcher and the participants. Additionally, it would be possible to interview or gather data from people anywhere in the world at a reasonable cost to the researcher and the participants. In addition, secondary data were collected from tender documents, BTB regulations, and circulars. This approach has allowed for a deeper comprehension of the procurement function within the company and is a productive technique to gather crucial information.

3.3.1.1 Pilot Study

To make certain that the questions were reliable and accurate, a pilot study was conducted. Piloting is crucial when creating a qualitative interview so that prospective interviewers may better grasp the questions being posed. According to Oppenheim (1992), piloting can assist interviewers with a variety of procedural issues, such as the introduction's layout, the sequencing of question sequences, the interview's time limits, and more. Every research study has possible interview design flaws; hence, it is essential that interview questions are tested with a small sample of participants before being employed. The experience contributes to the development of a well-rehearsed structure and gives the interviewers the chance to determine whether the interviewee finds the questions vague or perplexing (Jong & Jung, 2015).

The results of the pilot study were used to assess the instruments' appropriateness, accuracy, and clarity. Additionally, it helped to categorize elusive and ambiguous items so that those that failed to evaluate the intended variables have been changed. It was also a useful way for the researcher to get feedback from respondents, as they suggested altering and rephrasing some

questions that were slightly ambiguous and also verified that other questions were clear and concise. The pilot study has also helped in discovering the most proper methods for communicating with and contacting the interview candidates.

3.3.2. Quantitative Methods:

Quantitative data are by their very nature numerical, and they may be mathematically calculated. Numerous scales, including the nominal scale, ordinal scale, interval scale, and ratio scale, are used for measuring quantitative data. Through random sampling, the structured data collection methods utilized for quantitative data collection fit a range of experiences within specified categories of replies. They provide findings that are simple to sum up, contrast, and extrapolate (Kabir, 2016).

A secondary research approach was used to collect quantitative data, as it included data collected from official statistics, published materials, and archival records. According to studies cited by Asker & Battal (2017), airport operational efficiency can be measured using a variety of variables, including terminal size, runway length, and personnel count as inputs, and total passengers, total flights, total freight, and total revenue as outputs. Operational efficiency measures are important for organizations to evaluate how well they are using their resources and how they stack up against their competitors. BIA data were compared with other airports in the region to analyze its current situation.

3.4 Data Analysis:

3.4.1. Qualitative Data:

Thematic analysis was used to evaluate data from qualitative interviews. This has involved using tables to show patterns or themes, highlighting the sentences from each participant, and finally breaking the data into smaller segments or themes. The key conclusions from the BTB's legislation, decisions, and circulars were used to assess the documents.

Additionally, the BIC tenders that were issued and awarded were documented and studied in order to better understand the BIA operations and the typical procurement strategies. This is expected to make it easier to validate the results and the interview data. MAXDQA software was used to analyze the data. The use of secondary data could considerably boost creditability for the research as it provides support for interview results and could be used as a triangulation method.

3.4.2. Quantitative Data:

The most popular effectiveness measuring tool, Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), was utilized to analyze airport efficiency metrics. The DEA is built on a foundation of linear programming, and it assesses the relative effectiveness of decision-making units based on linear programming. The ratio of technically total weighted outputs to theoretically total weighted inputs is calculated by the DEA and compared to a limit that denotes optimal performance (Kocak, 2011).

Considering this, it is crucial to take into account the efficiency measurements that are required for the efficient and effective operation of airports with large investment costs, which are essential to the aviation industry, and to take the information gathered as a result of this measurement into account. The data was

analyzed using DEAFrontier software. Additionally, data and statistics about BIA and other airports were obtained from a number of sources, which has assisted in understanding BIA's position in relation to other airports in the region. Tables were used to present the findings in addition to a detailed explanation of the data.

3.5 Ethics

Interview questions have involved clear and neutral statements to avoid using the researcher's own assumptions about the topic. Participants in the interviews were required to fill out a research participant form. The data from interviews was analyzed using software to avoid personal bias. The data will be protected using a password, and it will be erased after 3 years from the completion of the research.

There needs to be assurance that taking part in the study will not have any negative consequences for the respondents, and nobody should be under any duress to take part in the interview. It is important to respect the respondents' right to secrecy and anonymity, as well as any prospective refusals to respond to specific questions. Therefore, no participant or organization was identified.

3.6 Chapter Summary:

A deeper and more extensive understanding of the research issue has resulted from the study's incorporation of a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches. Qualitative methods include semi-structured interviews that were conducted with various officials from BIA and were selected due to their relevant

experience and knowledge in the research area. Thematic analysis was used to examine the interviews, which involved breaking down the data into smaller portions and utilizing tables to display patterns and themes.

Quantitative techniques include the analysis of tender documents, archival data, and regulations that were used to corroborate the data gathered from the interview for a better understanding of the procurement process in BAC. The operational effectiveness of the BIA was compared to other airports in the region using DEA, which was used to evaluate quantitative data. In order to ensure that the results of qualitative research are credible and trustworthy, validity and reliability are crucial considerations for all researchers. Several steps were taken to assure that these aspects were committed to during the study.

CHAPTER FOUR

FINDINGS

Chapter 4: Findings

4.1 Introduction:

The research findings from both quantitative and qualitative methodologies are presented in this chapter. The findings of the analysis of archival documents and data from BTB and BAC websites are presented first in the following subsection, followed by the thematic analysis of the semi-structured interviews conducted with BAC staff, and later followed by the quantitative Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), which will be used to analyze airport efficiency metrics. Finally, the findings will be discussed to answer the research questions.

4.2 Qualitative Data Findings:

This section analyzes the legislation, decisions, and circulars of the BTB. This part also includes a thematic analysis of the personnel interviews with the procurement and operations personnel at BAC. Utilizing MAXDQA software, the interviews were transcribed and analyzed to help identify themes and separate the data into manageable portions.

4.2.1 Analysis of Archives:

To better comprehend Bahrain's tendering system and its procedures, the paper has examined archival documents and data from the BAC and BTB websites.

The findings from the documents will be used to validate the data from the interviews and give a thorough overview of the procedures that control the

procurement process in BAC. BTB's legislation, rulings, circulars, and guidelines are all contained in the archives and can be found at the BTB website.

Additionally, seven BAC RFPs (Requests for Proposals) on the BTB website were also reviewed to provide a better understanding of the BAC procurement process. Both the BAC and BTB websites were also reviewed to gather additional information about the tendering procedure. The data will be analyzed in the following subsection.

#	Document	Type
1	LEGISLATIVE DECREE NO.36 OF 2002 WITH RESPECT TO REGULATING GOVERNMENT TENDERS AND PURCHASES.	Law
2	DECREE NO.37 OF 2002 WITH RESPECT TO PROMULGATING THE IMPLEMENTING REGULATIONS OF THE LAW REGULATING GOVERNMENT TENDERS AND PURCHASES.	Law
3	Resolution No. (30) for the year 2022 For Issuing a Guide Regulating Partnerships between Public and Private Sectors.	Law
4	Guideline Manual for Purchasing Authorities. Government Tenders, Auctions, Purchases and Sales.	Guideline
5	RFP/BAC/2022/19	RFP
6	RFP/INT/BAC/2022/09	RFP
7	RFP/INT/BAC/2022/15	RFP
8	RFP/INT/BAC/2022/25	RFP
9	RFP/INT/BAC/2022/41	RFP
10	RFP/INT/BAC/202244	RFP
11	RFP/BAC/2022/26	RFP

Figure 3: Archival Documents to Be Used for Analysis

All government acquisitions and contracts in the Kingdom of Bahrain, including those with BAC, are processed through public tenders, which are overseen by an independent regulator (BTB). Regulations are put in place to make sure that all government procurement and tendering procedures are transparent, competitive, and fair to all parties. Anyone can access information about public tenders through Bahrain.bh or the BTB website.

Suppliers must be registered as qualified suppliers or contractors in order to qualify for a tender from your company. Suppliers must register in the e-Tendering System to gain access to the most recent tendering-related information for both local and foreign vendors (Government of Bahrain, 2021). According to the 2021 annual BTB report, twenty-eight tenders were issued for BAC in 2021, with a total amount of approximately 30 million BHD. This has made it the eighth highest-spending government agency in the year (Bahrain Tender Board, 2022).

4.2.1.1. Tendering Process Stages in Bahrain

First: Invitation Stage	The tender documents, approval from the Ministry of Finance and National Economy, and approval of the tender/auction invitation method form are uploaded and approved directly through the e-Tendering System.
Second: Evaluation Stage	After being opened by the board, the bids are given to the purchasing authority to review and assess. Next, a letter

	addressed to the board's chairman containing the evaluation of tender bids form and a thorough evaluation report for each bid received is submitted to the tender board with the purchase authority's evaluation.
Third: Negotiation Stage	If the bid price is higher than the estimated cost received, a committee will be formed to negotiate with the bidder whose offer received the highest score in terms of its technical and financial evaluation. The board receives a formal letter outlining the outcomes of the negotiations.
Fourth: Post Award Stage	The bid with the best conditions and lowest price receives the tender from the board. The winning supplier must be informed of the tender in order to submit the performance bond to the purchasing authority. A contract must be signed with the supplier accordingly, and once the terms of the contract have been fulfilled, the performance bond must be returned to the supplier.

Figure 4: Stages of Public Procurement in Bahrain, derived from the Tender Board Guideline Manual for Purchasing Authorities (Bahrain Tender Board, 2022).

4.2.1.1. Supplier Pre-Qualification:

According to Decree No. 37 of 2002 With Respect To Promulgating The Implementation Regulations Of The Law Regulating Government Tender And Purchases, authorities subject to the regulations must work only with suppliers and contractors who satisfy all of their requirements for goods, construction work, or services and who have the necessary credentials, professional,

technical, and financial capabilities, as well as the necessary equipment, such as machinery, appliances, and other items, in addition to the necessary expertise to carry out the purchase contract. All suppliers must prove their qualifications by submitting the required documents, which will be validated by a committee of professional members. This is an important step that ensures that BAC and other government entities will deal with capable and certified suppliers, which would minimize the risk of noncompliance.

4.2.1.2. RFPs Analysis

RFPs (Requests for Proposals) are included on the BTB website, where BAC tenders can be sorted and reviewed. Each RFP will detail the required specifications that bidders have to comply with. One instance is the passenger market research survey request, which requires the bidder to demonstrate their expertise in conducting this kind of market research for corporations and supplying consulting services, as well as to submit a proposal that contains at least 50% primary-based research and 50% secondary research.

Another example is the request for the supply of warehouse outsourced storekeepers for 5 years, which included the requirements that storekeepers be available to cover 24/7 warehouse operations for the duration, as well as the provision of a 24/7 response team and a manager who would serve as the point of contact for any problems or concerns. Other RFPs will require completed BoQs (Bills of Quantity), signed appendix, and a clear cost breakdown. Some RFPs will include detailed descriptions which will be available to registered suppliers on the BTB website. Each RFP will include instructions on how to

participate in it, along with the tender fees, initial bond, and deadline for submission.

4.2.1.3. Evaluation of Proposals.

Resolution No. (30) for the year 2022 For Issuing a Guide Regulating Partnerships between Public and Private Sectors states that the contracting administrative entity is required to create a report outlining the order of proposals based on the evaluation results. In order to evaluate each proposal in accordance with the assessment criteria and the proportionate weight of each criterion that are provided in the request for proposals document, the ministry shall collaborate with the contracting administrative entity. The minimum value of the threshold may be defined by the contracting administrative entity taking into account technical, financial, and commercial factors. The minimum requirement must be met for proposals to qualify. This should ensure that the qualified bids match all the requirements as per the criteria set in the RFP document, and only suppliers that provide the minimal requirements can participate in the bids.

4.2.1.4. Project Supervision:

Resolution No. (30) for the year 2022 For Issuing a Guide Regulating Partnerships between Public and Private Sectors also states that the partnership contract specifies requirements, standards, arrangements, preparations, and performance indicators. The contracting administrative entity is tasked with carrying out duties pertaining to the oversight of the project implementation phases, ensuring the attainment of the highest levels of performance necessary,

assessing the performance of the supplier, and maintaining the accessibility of those requirements, standards, preparations, and performance indicators. The contracting administrative entity shall notify the supplier of any deviations from the required quality and performance standards and needed performance indicators and shall request the supplier to take corrective action within a specified time period.

The contracting administrative entity has the authority to terminate the partnership agreement if the supplier is unable to perform its responsibilities or makes it appear that it is not willing to do so owing to insolvency, breach, other factors, or considerations linked to the public interest. The partnership agreement shall specify the process for calculating the compensation due to each party in the event of contract termination. These provisions are intended to safeguard the public interest and protect the entity from noncompliance risk.

4.2.2. Interview Analysis:

The analysis of the semi-structured interviews is presented in this section with the goal of gathering comprehensive information from BAC procurement and operations staff about procurement and operations performance inside the organization. Major themes and concepts from the thematic analysis of the interviews are presented in the ensuing subsections. Code frequency has helped to improve understanding of the context of the phenomenon and could be sufficient to shed light on new insights, but its significance was not stressed in the data analysis. Interview data was analyzed by MAXDQA Software. Interview questions are included in the appendix.

The figure below provides information regarding the participants; since their identities will not be revealed, they will be referred to by their reference number.

Reference	Department
Interviewee #1	Procurement
Interviewee #2	Procurement
Interviewee #3	Procurement
Interviewee #4	Operations
Interviewee #5	Operations

Figure 5: Participant Selection

4.2.2.1. Procurement Personnel Interviews:

	Procurement Roles	Supplier Evaluation Criteria	Issues	Risk Management	Procurement Process KPI
Interviewee #1	4	9	2	1	3
Interviewee #2	8	5	1	1	3
Interviewee #3	7	8	1	5	3

Figure 6: Thematic Analysis of Procurement Personnel Interviews, produced by MAXDQA Software.

Identifying potential sources of supply.	Interviewees #2 & #3
Risk management.	Interviewees #2 # #3
Process improvement.	Interviewee #2
Ensuring ethical compliance.	Interviewees #2 & #3
Managing the procurement process.	Interviewee #3
Ensuring compliance with contractual obligations.	Interviewees #2 & #3
Developing and maintaining supplier relationships.	Interviewee #3
Identify cost-saving opportunities.	Interviewee #3

Figure 8: BAC Procurement Roles and Responsibilities

4.2.2.1.2. Advantages of the Procurement Function:

Interviewee #1 has indicated that the procurement function has an insight into the market in terms of alternative products and suppliers to maintain business continuity and consistency. It also ensures to provide advice on the best procurement approach to achieve this goal. Interviewee #2 has cited three main advantages for the procurement functions: risk management by assessing and mitigating procurement risks; process improvement by continuously evaluating and improving the procurement process to enhance efficiency, reduce cost, and streamline operations; and ensuring ethical compliance. Interviewee #3 has indicated that effective procurement can foster strong relationships with suppliers, which could lead to better collaboration and access to new technologies. Selecting reliable suppliers that provide high-quality goods and

services is part of procurement's role in upholding standards for products and services. Procurement also helps lower supply chain risks and improves supply chain resilience to disruptions by managing suppliers and finding alternate sources. Interviewee #3 also agreed with interviewee #2 that procurement ensures compliance with ethical standards by minimizing legal and reputational risks.

4.2.2.1.3. Procurement Alignment With The Business Plan:

Interviewees were asked how they think the procurement function fits into the overall business plan. Interviewees #1 and #2 both stated that they are aware of requests and projects that have happened in the past and will happen in the future, as well as market changes and the influx of new suppliers. Interviewee #3 has cited four different indicators: Cost Optimization: by sourcing goods and services at the lowest feasible cost, negotiating favorable contracts, and implementing cost-control mechanisms; Risk Mitigation: by identifying and reducing risks related to suppliers, markets, and supply chains; Supply Chain Management: by ensuring reliable supply chains and minimizing disruption; and finally Strategic Partnership: by forging strong relationships with suppliers, procurement can help with innovation and the development of new products.

4.2.2.1.4. Main Issues That Face the Procurement Function:

Interviewees were asked about the key issues that face the procurement function and how they are dealt with. All interviewees agreed that lack of planning from stakeholders is the main issue because it can lead to urgent

requests. The interviewees also agreed that dealing with such issues requires proper planning and communicating with stakeholders to explain the benefits of proper planning in advance. Interviewee #1 also cited incomplete or vague requests from stakeholders as a major issue. This can be dealt with by helping end users identify the required specifications, as generalized specifications can allow a larger pool of suppliers to participate in bid.

4.2.2.1.5. Supplier Evaluation Criteria:

Interviewees have listed the below indicators as the main criteria for supplier evaluation.

Criteria	Source
Reliability	Interviewee #1
Competitiveness	Interviewees #1, #2 & #3
Value for Money	Interviewees #1 & #2
Quality of Products/Services	Interviewees #1 & #3
Financial Stability	Interviewees #1, #2 & #3
Governance	Interviewee #1
Corporate social responsibility	Interviewee #1
Ethics	Interviewees #1 & #3
Change Adoption	Interviewee #2
Experience & reputation	Interviewee #3
Lead/Delivery Time	Interviewee #3
Cooperation and Flexibility	Interviewee #3
Communication and response time	Interviewee #3

Figure 9: BAC Supplier Evaluation Criteria

4.2.2.1.6. Procurement Risk Mitigation:

Interviewee #1 has asserted that risks are inevitable and can be mitigated with proper planning and implementation of proper procedures, while interviewee #2 agreed that the implementation of procurement policy and being aware of all requirements and requests should be sufficient to manage risks. Interviewee #3 listed 5 strategies that can be used to mitigate risks: identifying potential risks, assessing their impact, developing risk management strategies, monitoring supplier performance, and managing supplier relationships.

4.2.2.1.7. Procurement Effect on Operational Efficiency:

Regarding the procurement effect on operational efficiency, interviewee #1 commented, "*Procurement can affect operational efficiency by considering the lead time required to complete any transaction. Procurement can delay or fasten any project*". Interviewee #2 has agreed on the same concepts. Interviewee #3 has stated that implementing an efficient procurement process shortens cycle times, eliminates manual errors, and improves process efficiency. Organizations can also benefit from cost reduction with the help of procurement's strategic sourcing, negotiation skills, and cost control measures. Last of all, tight cooperation with suppliers promotes better communication and quicker problem solving, which ought to lead to smoother operations.

4.2.2.1.8. Procurement Effect on Organizational Performance:

According to interviewee #1, procurement can impact organizational performance by ensuring that projects and businesses are running as efficiently as possible. Interviewee #2 has stated that being proactive and efficient can have a positive impact on organizational performance. Interviewee #3 has indicated that effective procurement practices can lead to cost savings, increased profitability, the timely availability of goods and services, downtime reduction, and improved customer satisfaction. In addition, the strategic objectives of the organization are supported by procurement's contribution to supplier selection and strategic sourcing, which can foster favorable organizational performance.

4.2.2.1.9. BAC Procurement Measurement KPI:

All the interviewees agreed that 3 KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) are used to measure the procurement performance in BAC: lead time, cost saving, and response to requests.

4.2.2.2. Operations Personnel Interviews:

	Risk Mitigation	Operational Efficiency Criteria	Challenges	Strategies	Operations Roles
Interviewee #4	3	2	1	1	5
Interviewee #5	3	3	1	10	5

also added that slot allocation and processing efficiency will be negatively impacted by an underperforming operations team, while in contrast, an exceptionally effective team can help save resources and enhance the airport's annual capacity.

4.2.2.2.2. Procurement Impact on Operations:

Interviewee #4 commented that procurement has sufficient knowledge to find the best vendors in terms of quality and price and also makes sure that a fair technical and financial evaluation is conducted based on the board's directives while monitoring other relevant factors. Interviewee #5 indicated that procurement improves operational efficiency through strong supplier relationships, cost control, and material availability. He also added that procurement helps reduce risks, expedite procedures, and encourage sustainability and compliance. These actions collectively lead to more efficient and cost-effective operations.

4.2.2.2.3. Strategies to Improve Operational Efficiency:

Interviewee #4 has asserted that the main approach to improving operational efficiency in BAC is maximizing available data. He added, *'By promoting Data-Driven Decision Making (DDDM) across the organization, process improvements/optimization opportunities for day-to-day operations can be identified, and strategic decisions will be supported by factual logic rather than biased opinions.'* Interviewee #5 has listed ten strategies to improve operational efficiency: supply chain management, continuous improvement, process

optimization, technology integration, resource allocation, training, performance metrics, customer focus, and risk management.

4.2.2.2.4. Main Challenges That Face Operations:

Both interviewees agreed that the main issue that faced operations was the shift from the old terminal to the new one, despite the extensive preparations and planning. The change was met with resistance as certain tasks were performed in the same manner for decades. Rather than enforcing a change, this was addressed by demonstrating potential benefits. Those who had previously opposed change have become its advocates by winning their support and making sure that all necessary conditions for change management are met.

4.2.2.2.5. Operations Alignment with the Company's Strategy:

Interviewee #4 asserted that the company's overall strategy is to establish itself as a major competitor both on a regional and international scale, and operations serve as the core of any initiative on a strategic level. In addition to enhancing customer satisfaction and lowering costs through operational optimization, efficient operations can attract new airlines. The operations function is at the forefront of emergency situations; therefore, it possesses the capacity to either positively or negatively impact the reputation of the country, not simply the airport, in the event of a crisis. Interviewee #5 commented *“The operations at BAC align with the company's strategy by ensuring efficient processes, timely services, and a strong focus on customer satisfaction; this supports the company's goal of delivering a world-class airport experience.”*

4.2.2.2.6. Operations Efficiency Measurement Criteria:

Both interviewees indicated that the main criterion for operational efficiency measurement is slot utilization. To assess its utilization, the airport's capacity for each processing zone must be measured, and then the passenger throughput must be taken into account. One example of poor utilization and its impact is if the aircraft parking slots were filled but only had a small number of passengers, then this would be considered poor utilization, and other airport processing points would be barely utilized at all. This indicates that the company will not be able to enhance passenger throughput and earn additional revenue per passenger.

4.2.2.2.7. Operational Efficiency Impact on Organizational Performance:

Interviewee #4 stated, *“Operational efficiency can reduce the number of resources needed, allow airports to surpass their designed capacities, improve airline On-Time Performance (OTP) and avoid unnecessary facility utilization. This will ultimately lead to reduced costs, an improved customer experience, and the opening of new revenue-generating streams. Hence, optimizing operational points is essential, and it is a continuous process”*. Interviewee #5 argued that operational efficiency can improve organizational performance by lowering costs, boosting service timeliness, ensuring quality, increasing revenue, gaining a competitive edge, encouraging innovation, and enhancing the customer experience; this will result in smoother operations and a stronger competitive position for the airport.

4.2.2.2.8. Operations Alignment with Other Departments:

Department	Function	Source
Facility Management	Coordinate with operations to identify off-peak hours before the closing slot for preventive maintenance.	Interviewees #4 & #5
Commercial	Work hand-in-hand with operations to improve the airport capacity and airline performance to attract new customers.	Interviewees #4 & #5
Security/ Safety	Work closely with operations to improve the airport's facilitation without compromising safety or security.	Interviewees #4 & #5

Figure 12: Procurement Alignment with Other Departments

4.2.2.2.9. Operational Risk Mitigation:

Both interviewees pointed out that the main measure for risk mitigation is short-term, and long-term planning which involve estimating the number of passengers expected based on events and identifying peak periods based on flight schedules. They concluded that by foreseeing uncertainty and making advance

plans, this proactive approach reduces operational risks while optimizing resource use and preparing the airport for peak demand.

4.3. Quantitative Data Findings:

In this section, DEA analysis will be used to measure the operational efficiency of BIA. It is the most widely used technique, and it is often used to examine the performance of airports. Various inputs and outputs were used in numerous studies measuring the efficiency of airports around the world. For this study, the inputs used are the number of runways, terminal area, and number of gates while the outputs are the total number of passengers, total freight, and total number of flights, all based on the statistics taken for the year 2022. The study also compares the performance of BIA to that of four other airports in the region in order to benchmark it against competitors and review its position in the market. Statistics were derived from airports' official websites and websites specializing in airport data. The data were analyzed using DEA Frontier software.

Airport	Number of Runways	Terminal Area	Number of Gates
Bahrain International Airport (BIA)	2	219,000 Sqm	24 (Bahrain Airport Company, 2023)
Dubai International Airport (DXB)	2	2,122,474 Sqm	61 (Dubai Airports, 2023)
Muscat International Airport (MCT)	2	580,000 Sqm	29 (Muscat International)

			Airport, 2019)
King Khaled International Airport (KKIA)	2	375,000 Sqm	40 (Riyadh Airports, 2023)
Hamad International Airport (HIA)	2	600,000 Sqm	41 (Hamad International Airport, 2023)

Figure 13: Inputs Used for DEA Analysis

Airport	Total Number of Passengers	Total Number of Flights	Total Freight (Tons)
Bahrain International Airport (BIA)	6,900,000	82,000	379,000 (Bahrain International Airport, 2023)
Dubai International Airport (DXB)	66,000,000	343,000	1,700,000 (Dubai Airports, 2023)
Muscat International Airport (MCT)	8,600,000	76,000	158,000 (Oman Airports, 2023)
King Khaled International Airport (KKIA)	27,000,000	193,000	600,000 (General Authority For Statistics, 2023)
Hamad International Airport (HIA)	36,000,000	218,000	2,300,000 (Hamad International

			Airport, 2023)
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Figure 14: Outputs Used for DEA Analysis

Input-Oriented CCR Model	Input-Oriented BCC Model
$\text{Max } \theta_0 = \sum_{j=1}^m u_j y_{j0}$	$\text{Max } \theta_0 = \sum_{j=1}^m u_j y_{j0} + u_0$
$\text{subject to } \sum_{i=1}^s v_i x_{i0} = 1$	$\text{subject to } \sum_{i=1}^s v_i x_{i0} = 1$
$\sum_{j=1}^m u_j y_{jk} - \sum_{i=1}^s v_i x_{ik} \leq 0$	$\sum_{j=1}^m u_j y_{jk} - \sum_{i=1}^s v_i x_{ik} + u_0 \leq 0$
$v_i \geq 0, u_j \geq 0, u_0 \text{ free in sign}$	$v_i \geq 0, u_j \geq 0, u_0 \text{ free in sign}$

Figure 15: Input-Oriented CCR Model and Input-Oriented BCC Model (Aminuddin & Ismail, 2016)

Two DEA models that can be used to assess efficiency are the CCR model and the BCC model. One of these models, the input-oriented model, seeks to minimize inputs while at least meeting the desired output level. The output-oriented model is an iteration of the model that attempts to enhance outputs while using no more inputs than were actually observed. Since airports seek to offer their consumers high-quality service while utilizing fewer resources, the input-oriented model version is suitable for this research. The input-oriented CCR model and the input-oriented BCC model will be used to evaluate airport efficiency. The main distinction between the BCC and CCR models is how returns to scale are taken into account. Constant returns to scale are used as the

basis for the evaluation of the CCR version. The BCC version allows for scaling of variable returns and is more versatile (Tari et al, 2016).

The models are shown in multiplier form in Figure 5 above, where θ denotes the relative efficiency score for DMU₀, x_{i0} the vector of input at DMU₀, y_{j0} the vector of output at DMU₀, x_{jk} the actual value of input i used by DMU_k, and y_{jk} the real value of output j produced by DMU_k. The weights that are associated with inputs and outputs are u and v , respectively. If $\theta = 1$, DMU is CCR/BCC-efficient. DMU₀ is not CCR/BCC-efficient otherwise. More than one DMU may occasionally be demonstrated to be efficient. By prioritizing the most effective DMUs, the super-efficiency technique is employed to solve this problem. Through the removal of constraints pertaining to the DMU that is being evaluated, this strategy alters the model above. The ideal DMU to use at the airport is the one with the highest Super Efficiency Score.

4.3.1 CCR Model Findings:

The highest ratio of weighted outputs to weighted inputs can be used to determine a DMU's efficiency in the CCR model, given that this ratio is the same for all DMUs and is less than or equal to one. The DEA model must be run n times, once for each DMU, to establish the relative efficiency of all DMUs. The CCR model evaluates scale and technical efficiencies using the ratio form's optimum value. Since the CCR envelopment has constant returns to scale, an increase in inputs causes an equal rise in outputs (Toloo & Nalchigar, 2009).

DMU No.	DMU Name	<i>Input Slacks Number of Airways</i>	<i>Terminal Size</i>	<i>Number of Gates</i>	<i>Output Slacks Total Number of Passengers</i>	<i>Total Number of Flights</i>	<i>Total Freight (Tons)</i>
1	BIA	0.737	0.000	0.000	8878425.656	0.000	27413.994
2	DXB	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
3	MCT	0.489	0.000	0.000	6023906.706	0.000	218676.385
4	KKIA	0.591	0.000	0.000	10137026.239	0.000	356559.767
5	HIA	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Figure 16: CCR Model Input Target

The efficient input target alludes to the goal that each airport should hit in order to achieve efficiency in both input and output. This demonstrates the input model that must be used in order to make the airport efficient. For efficient airports, the input levels stay the same. BIA for constant output requires 14.583 additional gates (rounded to 15) to achieve efficiency. The output of BIA can therefore be increased by the same level. All inefficient airports are susceptible to similar conclusions. Slack values and target values are different. Slacks display discrepancies, while the targets' summaries show the expected value.

DMU No.	DMU Name	Input-Oriented				
		CRS Efficiency	<i>Sum of lambdas</i>	<i>RTS</i>	<i>Optimal Lambdas with Benchmarks</i>	
1	BIA	0.608	0.239	Increasing	0.239	DXB
2	DXB	1.000	1.000	Constant	1.000	DXB
3	MCT	0.466	0.222	Increasing	0.222	DXB
4	KKIA	0.858	0.563	Increasing	0.563	DXB
5	HIA	1.000	1.000	Constant	1.000	HIA

Figure 17: CCR Model Slacks

The model slack describes the increase or decrease in each input needed for each airport to achieve efficiency; however, DXB and HIA have already achieved

efficiency and will not need any further input. This value illustrates the difference between the input and output variables' proportionate or constant changes. It also represents the potential value of input and output improvements. The graphic shows that for BIA to become efficient, its input needs to be increased or decreased by 0.73712 units (rounded to 1). Only the variable difference between the input and output is seen in slacks. Only the perception that the value must change—either upward or downward—remains.

DMU No.	DMU Name	Input-Oriented				
		CRS Efficiency	<i>Sum of lambdas</i>	<i>RTS</i>	<i>Optimal Lambdas with Benchmarks</i>	
1	BIA	0.608	0.239	Increasing	0.239	DXB
2	DXB	1.000	1.000	Constant	1.000	DXB
3	MCT	0.466	0.222	Increasing	0.222	DXB
4	KKIA	0.858	0.563	Increasing	0.563	DXB
5	HIA	1.000	1.000	Constant	1.000	HIA

Figure 18: Input-Oriented CCR Efficiency

This figure indicates that only DXB and HIA are the only efficient airports within the list, as they have a score of 1 while the score of BIA and the other two airports is less than 1. BIA will need to improve its efficiency by 39% to reach efficiency. This suggests that it must enhance its input variable, which they can do by either lowering or raising the input levels. Benchmarks mean that all airports except for HIA are benchmarked against DXB. It indicates an efficient airport to follow or use as a reference. Inefficient airports such as BIA can follow the input-output trend of DXB. But efficient airports don't have to follow any airport. BIA can follow 24% of the input from DXB to reach efficiency.

The RTS is a scale that depicts an output increase that is proportional to an input increase. An economic metric that can be used to gauge efficiency is the RTS. If a DMU can increase outputs while using the same number of inputs or maintain output levels with fewer inputs, it is considered efficient.

4.3.2. BCC (VRS) Model Findings:

DMU No.	DMU Name	Efficient Input Target Number of Airways	Terminal Size	Number of Gates	Efficient Output Target Total Number of Passengers	Total Number of Flights	Total Freight (Tons)
1	BIA	2	0	24	6900000	82000	379000
2	DXB	2	0	61	66000000	343000	1700000
3	MCT	2	0	29	15458824	122000	944000
4	KKIA	2	0	40	34288235	210000	2187000
5	HIA	2	0	41	36000000	218000	2300000

Figure 19: Input-Oriented BCC (VRS) Model Target

The figure demonstrates the input that each DMU should reach to achieve efficiency; in BCC analysis, the input is sufficient for BIA to reach efficiency.

DMU No.	DMU Name	Input Slacks Number of Airways	Terminal Size	Number of Gates	Output Slacks Total Number of Passengers	Total Number of Flights	Total Freight (Tons)
1	BIA	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	DXB	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	MCT	0	0	0	6858824	46000	786000
4	KKIA	0	0	0	7288235	17000	1587000
5	HIA	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 20: Input-Oriented BCC (VRS) Model Slack

According to the figure, no airport needs to change its input, as they all have already reached efficiency.

<i>DMU No.</i>	<i>DMU Name</i>	<i>Input-Oriented VRS Efficiency</i>	Optimal Lambdas with Benchmarks			
1	BIA	1.000	1.000	BIA		
2	DXB	1.000	1.000	DXB		
3	MCT	1.000	1.000	MCT		
4	KKIA	1.000	0.528	BIA	0.426	DXB 0.045 MCT
5	HIA	1.000	1.000	HIA		

Figure 21: Input-Oriented BCC (VRS) Efficiency

The figure demonstrates that all airports in the list are efficient, as their efficiency is 1. KKIA should use the other airports as a reference to improve. The BCC models seem to be more flexible for efficiency when comparing the CRS findings with the BCC findings. This difference between the CRS and VRS models was observed in the results for BIA, as BCC has asserted that it is efficient, while its efficiency level in CRS is 61%.

4.4 Discussion:

The section below discusses the findings that are derived from the main research questions:

Research Question #1: How can the procurement performance of BAC be measured?

Based on the interview analysis, the results suggest that the main factors that influence procurement performance in BAC are lead time, cost savings, and response to requests. These findings are aligned with Lardenoije's (2005) findings, who argued that the degree to which purchasing is able to guarantee the supply of goods in accordance with internal customers' needs against the

best condition determines purchasing performance on an operational level, while on a strategic level it can be determined by the extent it can support the organization's levels of innovation, quality, flexibility, and cost. Van Weele (2014) suggested that the main four dimensions to be considered for procurement performance measurement are cost, quality, delivery time, and impact on the organization's achievement of its goals. The study also suggests that the procurement function in BAC plays an important role in the improvement of overall organizational performance by contributing to supplier selection and strategic sourcing and ensuring that projects are running efficiently, which can lead to cost savings and increased profitability.

The procurement function is also aligned with the overall business plan, with the main indicators being cost optimization, risk mitigation, supply chain management, and building strong relationships with suppliers. As stated by Armstrong (2011), cost management is one of the main ways that the procurement department can support a business in maintaining a competitive advantage, as the company's profit is directly impacted by effective control of input cost expenses. Another way to develop strong relationships with suppliers, which can help enhance material quality and timely delivery and support the business if a sudden rise in business requirements occurs.

The analysis of archival documents from BTB and BAC has indicated that the procurement process in BAC, alongside the public institutions, goes through an intricate process to ensure that all the governmental procedures are transparent and fair to all parties. The regulations set critical procedures to ensure that only

contractors who can satisfy all the requirements and have all the necessary credentials can participate in the bidding to reduce contract noncompliance risks. All the bids will be reviewed based on assessment criteria by the contracting administrative entity to ensure that they match all the requirements and that only suppliers that fulfill the minimum requirements can participate. As indicated by Xin (2019), some of the most important public procurement fundamentals are value for money, which indicates that public organizations must develop their policies based on the best return on their investment; transparency, which refers to the openness and fairness of the procurement system that ensures accountability and minimizes the chance of corruption; and competition, which refers to the establishment of procedures to ensure competitive bidding for products and services.

Research Question #2: How can the operational efficiency of BAC be measured?

The study utilized the interview answers and the DEA technique to measure the operational efficiency of BIA and also compared the results to those of four other airports in the region to benchmark against competitors. The interview analysis indicates that slot utilization is the main criterion that is used to measure the operational efficiency of BIA; other considerations would include the airport's capacity for each processing zone and passenger throughput. Poor resource utilization would have a negative impact on the whole processing units and the airport's aim to increase throughput and revenue per passenger. Hillier (2012) stated that operational efficiency is the ratio of outputs realized by a firm to the

input required to execute a business operation, and the output-input ratio improves as operation efficiency increases. For BIA, the input is aircraft parking slots, airport processing units, capacity, and the output is passenger throughput and revenue per passenger.

The interview analysis also indicates that BIA can benefit from improved operational efficiency by exceeding its planned capacity, minimizing resource waste, and improving OTP and facility utilization, which eventually will lead to improved profits, enhanced customer satisfaction, and a competitive edge for the airport. This is supported by Oral & Yolalal (1990) and Sufian (2007), who asserted that a company's cash flow, profitability, and competitiveness can all increase as improved operational efficiency leads to reduced costs, and boosting operational efficiency has a direct impact on an organization's profit margins because profitable companies are more efficient.

Two methods were used in DEA analysis for BIA operational efficiency: the input-oriented CCR model and the input-oriented BCC model, using the number of runways, terminal area, and number of gates as input and the total number of passengers, flights, and total freight (tons) as output. Doganis (1992) asserts that performance measures are required in order to determine the airport's financial standing, gauge its performance, and evaluate how well its resources are managed. They also allow the efficacy of different airport departments to be compared with one another and with other airports.

The CCR method has indicated that BIA is 61% sufficient and must increase its input variable, which can be done by lowering or increasing the input levels.

Among the 5 airports that were analyzed, BIA was in the fourth place, and only DXB and HIA have reached efficiency. On the other hand, the BCC method has indicated that BIA and all the other airports analyzed are efficient.

Research Question #3: What is the relationship between procurement performance and operational efficiency in BAC?

The findings suggest that procurement has a substantial impact on operational efficiency in BAC through identifying the best vendors in terms of price and quality and ensuring that a fair evaluation is conducted in accordance with the company's objectives. Procurement also impacts operational efficiency by building strong relationships with suppliers, controlling costs, improving material availability, speeding up processes, and reducing risks. Other factors include the lead time required to complete a transaction, as it can postpone or fasten any project; and eliminating manual errors to improve process efficiency.

Procurement can also help with strategic sourcing, negotiations with vendors, and cost control initiatives. Collectively, these actions could result in more efficient and cost-effective operations.

These findings are in line with Quayle (2006), who supported the notion that a well-managed procurement process not only improves overall operational efficiency and fulfills supply requirements as efficiently as possible, but it also increases net income and profitability. However, the effectiveness of any business objective can only be assessed by setting goals and monitoring the progress made toward those goals. He also asserted that a common purchasing goal is to receive orders on time, and any delivery disruption might cause a delay

in supply and reduce operational efficiency and profitability. Kakwezi & Nyoko (2019) argued that predicting needs, sourcing, monitoring supply, and other procurement actions could improve operational efficiency, and procurement procedures that maximize value while meeting end-user needs are considered successful.

4.5 Chapter Summary:

In this chapter, the findings of three instruments were presented; the first was findings from the analysis of archival data from BTB and BAC websites, which included legislation, decisions, and circulars. The findings from thematic analysis of semi-structured interviews with BAC procurement and operations personnel were shown later. A DEA analysis was conducted to measure the operational efficiency of BAC and compare it with other airports in the region, and finally, the chapter discussed the findings and addressed the main research questions.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSIONS

Chapter 5: Conclusions

5.1 Introduction:

The primary objectives of the study were to evaluate the procurement and operations performance of BAC and establish a link between them. This chapter discusses the summary of the conclusions based on the research questions and objectives and offers recommendations to BAC. It also provides suggestions for future research and discusses the limitations of the study.

5.2 Summary of Findings:

This section summarizes the main conclusions of the study. It examines how the study has addressed the main research objectives and questions. The section is organized based on the main research objectives.

5.2.1 Research Objective #1: Evaluation of Procurement Performance of BAC:

The findings imply that lead time, cost savings, and response to requests are the primary determinants of procurement performance in BAC. These are aligned with Van Weele's (2014) statement that cost, quality, delivery time, and influence on an organization's goal-achieving should be the primary four variables taken into account when measuring an organization's procurement performance. The study also indicates that by implementing strategic sourcing and proper supplier

selection, the procurement function can significantly enhance organizational performance and result in cost savings and higher profitability for the company.

The primary indicators of the procurement function's alignment with the entire business plan are supply chain management, risk minimization, cost optimization, and fostering strong supplier relationships. Since efficient control of input cost expenses directly affects the company's profit, Armstrong (2011) noted that cost management is one of the primary ways that the procurement department can support a firm in sustaining a competitive advantage.

The analysis of archival documents from BAC and BTB websites reveals a complex procurement process in BAC and public institutions, ensuring transparency and fairness. Regulations set strict procedures for contractors to participate in bidding, reducing noncompliance risks. Bidding is reviewed by the contracting administrative entity, ensuring minimum requirements are met. As stated by Xin (2019), public procurement fundamentals include value for money, transparency, and competition, ensuring accountability and competitive bidding for products and services.

5.2.2 Research Objective #2: Evaluation of Operational Efficiency at BAC:

The study concluded that the main criteria for BIA's efficiency are slot utilization, capacity for processing zones, and passenger throughput. Poor resource utilization negatively impacts the whole processing units and the airport's goal to increase throughput and revenue per passenger. As asserted by Hillier (2012),

operational efficiency is the ratio of outputs realized to inputs required for business operations.

The improvement in operational efficiency in BAC could result in exceeding capacity, minimizing resource waste, and improving OTP and facility utilization, which eventually leads to improved profits, customer satisfaction, and a competitive edge for the airport. This is supported by Oral & Yolalal (1990) and Sufiyan (2007), who stated that improved operational efficiency leads to cost reduction and increased profitability and competitiveness. The DEA analysis has shown contrasting results for the two methods used to evaluate operational efficiency at BAC. The input-oriented CCR model has indicated that BAC is 61% efficient, while the input-oriented BCC model has implied that the airport has reached efficiency.

5.2.3 Research Objective #3: Establishing a Link Between Procurement and Operational Efficiency:

The study reveals that procurement significantly enhances operational efficiency at BAC by identifying the best vendors, conducting fair evaluations, building strong supplier relationships, controlling costs, improving material availability, speeding up processes, and reducing risks. It also helps in strategic sourcing, vendor negotiations, and cost control initiatives, ultimately leading to more efficient and cost-effective operations. Quayle (2006) and Kakwezi & Nyoko (2019) emphasize the importance of well-managed procurement processes in improving operational efficiency, fulfilling supply requirements, and increasing net income and profitability. They argue that setting goals and monitoring

progress towards those goals is crucial for assessing the effectiveness of business objectives. They also highlight the importance of predicting needs, sourcing, and monitoring supply to improve operational efficiency and ensure successful procurement procedures.

5.2.4 Collective Summary of Conclusions:

The study evaluates the procurement performance of BAC, focusing on lead time, cost savings, and response to requests. It suggests that strategic sourcing and supplier selection can improve organizational performance, leading to cost savings and higher profitability. The procurement function aligns with the business plan through cost optimization and building strong relationships with suppliers. The study also evaluates operational efficiency at BAC, focusing on slot utilization, capacity for processing zones, and passenger throughput. The link between procurement and operational efficiency is established, emphasizing the importance of strategic sourcing and supply monitoring.

5.3 Recommendations:

5.3.1 Recommendations for the Procurement Function:

- Introduction of initiatives to increase automation in the procurement process, which can lead to improvements in efficiency and the minimization of manual errors.
- Deployment of predictive analytics to forecast demand and modify procurement strategies as necessary.

- Introduction of sustainability as one of the main factors in supplier selection to align with the company's strategy to improve sustainability and utilize resources efficiently.
- The application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) to automate repetitive processes, enhance data accuracy, and facilitate intelligent decision-making.
- Implementation of Supplier Collaboration Platform (SCP), which is a cloud-based software that enables companies to connect and collaborate with their suppliers. The platform offers businesses a safe, centralized location to share data and documents, handle supplier relationships, interact with suppliers, and monitor their performance.

5.3.2 Recommendations For the Operations Function:

- Collaboration with partners to launch new lucrative airline routes to improve passenger output and optimize the extended capacity of the new terminal.
- Developing plans to attract low-cost carriers to compete with Dubai and Abu Dhabi as the major transit hubs in the region.
- Building initiatives to increase automation for all manual processes in the airport to speed up processing time and improve throughput.
- Adoption of new technologies such as AI and ML to enhance the customer experience and predict passenger and cargo demand accurately.
- Implementation of energy-saving strategies and utilization of Negative Emission Technologies (NETs).

5.4 Suggestions for Future Research:

The study has analyzed the effect of the procurement process in BAC on its operational efficiency; future studies can focus on the financial implications of the procurement process in BAC and its effect on the company's profitability. Other studies can focus on the role of procurement in BAC for the successful implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Future research can also examine the procurement practices of other public entities in Bahrain, such as EWA (Electricity & Water Authority), CBB (Central Bank of Bahrain), and TRA (Telecommunications Regulatory Authority).

5.5 Limitations of the Study:

Limitations include the time limit to complete the study, which is 12 weeks, as it is not sufficient to get the insights of all the stakeholders in the airport industry, such as airline personnel, BAS (Bahrain Airport Services) personnel, customs clearance personnel, and The Ministry of Transport and Telecommunications. Additionally, the study's findings are exclusive to BIA and cannot be generalized to other airports. Some data might also have limited access and not be available to the public. Lastly, airport statistics were collected for the year 2022, and the airport industry still has not totally recovered from the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic; therefore, the results could be improved for the year 2023 and the following years.

5.6 Chapter Summary:

In conclusion, the chapter has presented a summary of findings based on the main research objectives and provided recommendations to improve the procurement and operations functions in BAC. It also provided suggestions for future research in important areas that need to be explored. Finally, the chapter discussed the main limitations that might have influenced the outcome and conclusions of the study.

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Appendix A – Taught Ethics Application Form

FIRST STAGE

Students engaging in any research activity should read the *Guidance Notes for Ethical Applications – Taught Programmes* and complete the *Ethics Approval of Taught Programmes Application Form* and **submit this, along with all relevant supporting documentation, to their supervisor**. The supervisor will then assess the application for any significant ethical issues. Please refer to the Guidance for Supervisors and the guidance notes for the students.

If there are no significant ethical issues to be considered and/or any minor issues have been fully resolved, the supervisor will sign off the ethics approval form, which should then be included with the final dissertation.

However, if the supervisor feels that the application falls outside the scope of supervisory approval i.e. the issues involved are considered to have a significant ethical dimension, then the application will be referred for review to the Ethics Approval Panel for Taught Programmes (**Second Stage**).

SECOND STAGE (Only applies to projects/dissertations with significant ethical issues)

The application will be reviewed independently by two members of the Ethics Approval Panel for Taught Programmes. One reviewer will be selected from the same subject area as the proposed dissertation and the other reviewer from outside this area.

Second Stage Applications should be sent via email to: SBS-TaughtEthics@salford.ac.uk

Following review, one of the following recommendations will be made:

- (a) **Application is approved with no changes;**
- (b) **Application is approved subject to conditions which must be approved by supervisor.** Applicant make the appropriate changes to the application and resubmits to their supervisor for approval;
- (c) **Application is approved, subject to conditions, which must be approved by committee chair.** The applicant makes the appropriate changes to the application and resubmits to the committee chair for approval;

(d) Application is rejected and applicant requested to resubmit to committee.

In cases where the reviewers offer different final recommendations the committee chair will act as the final arbiter in the decision process.

The normal turnaround time for applications is approximately two weeks following submission. However, this can be longer, depending upon the complexity and the time of year the application has been submitted. If the application is not approved and changes need to be made the overall process will take longer.

Instructions for use

Most applications for ethics approval will be able to be granted by the supervisor. **Students should just complete the Checklist and Part A below and forward to their supervisor, who will complete Part B.** In some cases, if the supervisor believes the proposal should be sent to the Ethics Approval Panel for Taught Programmes for guidance and clearance, Part C should be completed and sent to the email address provided above. Supervisors should send Parts A, B and C to the panel in these cases.

The following checklist is to help students and supervisors easily identify projects which may be designated as one with significant ethical dimensions.

SECTION I: CHECKLIST (select as appropriate)

Does the project/dissertation involve work with human tissue/body fluids?

NO

If **'NO'** skip to section (II)

<p>Does the project involve work with animals and/or animal tissue?</p> <p>If 'NO' skip to section (III)</p>	<p>NO</p>
<p>Does the project involve any of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruitment of volunteers? • Questionnaires or interviews? • Observations of Participants? <p>If Yes for either please complete the sections (IV)-(VI) below</p> <p>If No please complete section (VI) only</p>	<p>YES</p>
<p>SECTION II – RISK OF HARM AND RELATED ISSUES (select as appropriate)</p>	
<p>Is there any realistic risk of any participants experiencing either physical or psychological distress or discomfort?</p>	<p>NO</p>
<p>Are drugs, placebos or other substances (e.g. food substances, vitamins) to be administered to study participants?</p>	<p>NO</p>
<p>Is there any possible psychological risk to the researcher?</p> <p>(Note:- physical risks to the researcher are considered in the Risk Assessment not in this form)</p>	<p>NO</p>
<p>Will participants undergo sound exposure beyond the Lower Action Level of the Physical Agents Directive?</p>	<p>NO</p>

Does the project require the use of hazardous substances?	NO
Is the use of radiation (if applicable) over and above what would normally be expected (for example) in diagnostic imaging?	NO
SECTION III – VULNERABLE GROUPS AND FINANCIAL INDUCEMENTS (select as appropriate)	
Will financial inducements (other than reasonable expenses and compensation for time) be offered to participants?	NO
Will participants fall into any of the following special groups?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children (under 18 years of age); 	NO
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People with learning difficulties or communication difficulties; 	NO
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People who speak a different language; 	NO
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients or clinical populations and/or their carers; 	NO
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pregnant women or research on conception or contraception; 	NO
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People in custody or any form of detention; 	NO
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People engaged in illegal activities (e.g. drug-taking) 	NO
SECTION IV – OTHER (select as appropriate)	

<p>Are there any other potential significant ethical issues not covered above? If Yes, please give details below:</p>	<p>NO</p>
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PART A – To be completed by Student

<p>Full Programme Title:</p>	<p>MSc in Procurement, Logistics and Supply Chain Management</p>	<p>Award</p>
<p>Title of Research Project:</p>	<p>Procurement Performance and Its Impact on Operational Efficiency in Bahrain Airport Company</p>	
<p>Has this project received external funding?</p>	<p>If YES, please provide name of Research Council or other funding organisation: NO</p>	

<p>Do you use non-human genetic materials from outside UK for your research?</p>	<p>If YES, has this been collected since the 12th October 2014? NO</p>
<p>Does your study involve a clinical trial?</p>	<p>If YES, do you intend to register your trial on a clinical database? NO</p> <p>Please note that most academic journals will not publish trials which have not been registered on a clinical trial registry before the onset of patient enrolment. For the purposes of registration, a clinical trial is any research study that prospectively assigns human participants to one or more health-related interventions to evaluate the effects on health outcomes. “Interventions” covers any treatment which can affect an individual’s health, e.g. medical devices, behavioural treatments, dietary interventions, etc.</p> <p>For more details, see: http://www.icmje.org/recommendations/browse/publishing-and-editorial-issues/clinical-trial-registration.html</p>

1. Project Aims and Objectives:

Project Aims: The main aim of the study is to determine the impact of procurement performance of BAC on its operational efficiency.

Project Objectives: To evaluate the procurement performance of BAC, evaluate the operational efficiency of BAC, and to establish a link between the procurement function and the operational efficiency of BAC.

2. Research Methodology:

Primary research will be conducted by gathering new data to answer research questions. A case study approach will be used, which is a thorough investigation of a contemporary issue in its real-life context. The study will be done using a mixed methods approach that combines both quantitative and qualitative techniques.

3. Organisational Agreement (If applicable):

4. Approaching Individuals (If applicable):

Interviews will be conducted with personnel with supervisory roles in the procurement, tendering, and operations functions in Bahrain Airport Company (BAC) and Bahrain Tender Board (BTB) with at least 10 years of experience in their respective fields. They would be selected as they would have the best knowledge and experience for their roles.

5. How will you ensure 'informed consent' is gained from anyone involved in the research?

Interview participants will be asked to fill out a research participant form.

6. How will you approach General Data Protection Regulation issues during your research?

The data will be protected using a password, and it will be erased after 3 years from the completion of the research. It is important to respect the respondents' right to secrecy and anonymity, as well as any prospective refusals to respond to specific questions.

Therefore, no participant or organization will be identified.

7. Does this project require that the researcher applies for a Disclosure Barring Service (DBS) check?

If you have answered **YES** above, please cite the code and either include it as an appendix to this application or provide details below about where it can be consulted electronically.

NO

8. What other ethical issues should you consider when conducting this research and how will potential ethical risk/harm be avoided?

No participant will be identified, to avoid any potential risk on the individual involved.

9. Does the project involve human subjects (e.g. as volunteers or to take part in interviews/questionnaires) and/or animals and/or human tissue and/or animal tissue?

If **YES**, please give details:

Yes, interviews will be conducted with personnel from Bahrain Airport Company (BAC) and Bahrain Tender Board (BTB) to offer in-depth insights from professionals with solid expertise in public procurement.

PART B – Application Form for Ethics Approval for Taught Programmes

To be completed by Supervisor

To be completed by the supervisor by ticking the relevant box. If ethics approval is granted the supervisor should give this form to the student to include in their dissertation, along with Part A. Nothing further needs to be done with the application at this point. **However, if ethics approval is rejected by the supervisor they should consult with the student as to the required changes and complete Part C.**

Student's Full Name:	Munther Kamal Alddin
Title of Research and Project Focus:	Procurement Performance and Its

	Impact on Operational Efficiency in Bahrain Airport Company
Supervisor's Name:	Michael Ricco
Data application received by supervisor:	3 Sep 2023

Ethics Approval Granted	Please send copy of form to student to include in their dissertation	X
Ethics Approval Rejected	If rejected please consult with student as to the required changes	
Ethics Approval Referred	If supervisor has queries or concerns in relation to this application, please fill in Part C below and forward to the School Ethical Approval Panel for Taught	

	Programmes	
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PART C – To be completed by Supervisor

To be completed by the supervisor if significant ethical issues are identified, with an indication of the key issues and areas for approval, and forwarded, to the Research Centres Support Team (SBS-TaughtEthics@salford.ac.uk). The application will then go through the formal ethics approval process.

Title of Research and Project Focus:	
Supervisor's Name:	

Please provide a brief description of the key issues and areas within this application that you would like the Ethics Approval for Taught Programmes to consider:

Appendix B – Research Participant Consent Form

Title of Project: Procurement Performance in Bahrain Airport Company and its Impact on Operational Efficiency

Name of Researcher: Munther Kamalalddin

Researcher's email address: munther4@gmail.com

Name of Supervisor: Dr. Michael Ricco

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study and what my contribution will be.

Yes	No
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- I have been given the opportunity to ask questions

Yes	No
-----	----

- I agree to take part in the interview.

Yes	No
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- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I can withdraw from the research at any time **without giving any reason**

Yes	No
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- **I agree to take part in the above study**

Yes	No
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Name of participant:

Signature:

Date:

Appendix C – Interview Questions

For The Procurement Function:

- 1- What are the roles & responsibility of the Procurement function in the company?
- 2- What other advantages does the procurement function provide other than financial ones?
- 3- How do you think the company's procurement function fit into the overall business plan, and why?
- 4- What are the main issues that face the procurement function within the organization? And how might they be dealt with?
- 5- What are the main criteria for supplier evaluation?
- 6- What are the main steps to manage procurement and supplier risks?
- 7- How does procurement function affect operational efficiency in the organization?
- 8- How does the procurement performance affect the organizational performance in the company?
- 9- What KPIs are used to measure the procurement process in the company?

For the Operations Function:

- 1- What is the role of operations in the organization?
- 2- How does procurement contribute to the operational efficiency in the organization?

- 3- What is the company's strategy to improve operational efficiency?
- 4- What are the main challenges that the company that the company faced in operations? And how did it deal with them?
- 5- How does the operations role align with the company's strategy?
- 6- What are the criteria to measure the operational efficiency in the company?
- 7- How can operational efficiency improve organizational performance?
- 8- How is the operations process aligned with other departments in the company?
- 9- What measures did the company take to reduce operational risks in the airport?